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Impact Of Sport Psychological Preparation Module On Grassroots Sports Development In Delta State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the Impact of Psychological Preparation Modules on Grassroots Sports Development in Delta State, Nigeria. The objective was to determine how goal setting, stress management and relaxation techniques, focus and concentration training, motivation techniques, emotional regulation techniques, and confidence-building techniques contribute to the development of grassroots sports. A correlational research design was adopted, and from a total population of 2,743 comprising 2,344 athletes, 322 coaches and trainers, and 77 sports administrators in Delta State, 340 respondents including athletes, coaches, and sports administrators were purposively selected for the study. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection, and its reliability was confirmed through pilot testing (Cronbach's alpha = .847). Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27. The findings revealed strong and statistically significant positive relationships between all psychological preparation modules and grassroots sports development. Stress management and relaxation techniques had the highest correlation ($r = 0.997$), followed by focus and concentration training ($r = 0.985$), motivation techniques ($r = 0.976$), emotional regulation techniques ($r = 0.945$), confidence-building techniques ($r = 0.839$), and goal setting ($r = 0.745$). All null hypotheses were rejected at $p < 0.01$, confirming that these psychological variables significantly influence grassroots sports development in the area studied. Based on these findings, the study recommends, among others: integrating psychological modules into coaching programmes; organizing periodic mental training seminars and workshops to educate stakeholders on the benefits of psychological preparedness; implementing customized goal-setting programmes to build cohesion and purpose; and incorporating mindfulness, relaxation, and stress management activities into daily training to help athletes manage performance anxiety.

Keywords: psychological preparation module, sports administrators, grassroots sports development

INTRODUCTION

Sports serve as a platform for fostering physical health, social cohesion and individual development within communities worldwide. In fact, sport is defined as all form of physical activity which, through casual or organized participation, aim at expressing or improving physical fitness and mental well-being, forming social relationships, or obtaining results in competition at all levels (Association for Applied

Sport Psychology, 2024). It is also described as a physical activity engaged in for pleasure (Merriam-Webster, 2020). The International Olympic Committee (2020) defines sport as all forms of physical activity that aim to improve physical fitness and mental well-being, and that contribute to social inclusion and personal success

In Nigeria, grassroots sports development has been increasingly recognized for its potential to foster social cohesion, youth's empowerment, and talent emergence from the community level (Efebeh, 2020; Kroot et al., 2024). Efebeh (2020) emphasizes that community-level sports can serve as powerful tools for promoting unity, trust, and economic opportunity among youth in fragmented societies. Kroot et al. (2024), in a study of a Lagos-based "Basketball Experience" program, report that integration of resilience and mental-health modules including mindfulness and breathing exercises helped reduce mental-health stigma and enhance well-being and life-skill development among participants.

Despite its benefits, grassroots sports development in Delta State remains constrained owing not only to infrastructure and funding limitations, but also to inadequate psychological preparedness of participants. This aligns with findings by Demeke and Beyene (2024), whose experimental study showed that structured psychological skill training (e.g., goal setting, anxiety reduction) significantly improved motivation and reduced anxiety among U-17 football players. Moreover, Ochor and Amasiatu (2024) note that Nigerian athletes frequently contend with stress and performance anxiety tied to societal expectations, financial insecurity, and mental-health stigma.

According to Odegbami (2020), Nigeria's National Sports Festival was incorporated into the nation's social fabric as one of the tools used to lessen the hurt, resentment, and other effects of the civil war that raged from 1967 to 1970. To that degree, sports can encourage and maintain harmonious cohabitation between a diverse population. Emeka et al. (2016) plainly stated that one beautiful thing about sport is that it shelves the idea of political ideologies, ethnicity or religion. Nwankwo et al. (2016) noted that sports in Nigeria have evolved from a modest beginning as an entertainment and recreational temporary activity to a prominent phenomenon and a lucrative gold mine, cutting disparities among ethnic nationalities and regions through its impart; and capturing diversities, by its influence felt in all spheres of lives of the citizenry. Okediji (2015), observed that "sports, be it soccer or any other game, has cut across all barriers; ethnic, religious, or racial and has served as a symbolic conversation in developing the youths." Sports have had such a profound and significant impact on the unity and integration of the Nigerian state. Sports have been used by great nations to help their young people grow in ways that science, religion and politics have not been able to. Sport performance is determined by a complex interaction of variables that particularly include physiological, biomechanical and tactical considerations (Glazier, 2015). In Nigeria, and particularly in Delta State, sports have historically played a role in cultural expression, community bonding, crime reduction, and national identity (Amaefule & Ikuejamoye, 2016).

The systematic development of grassroots sport is essential for nurturing young talent and promoting sporting excellence, faces multifaceted challenges that hinder its potential impact. Numerous sports icons, such as Pelé, who founded the Pelé Foundation to support education and sports for underprivileged children in Brazil, and Serena Williams, who promotes education and empowerment for young girls through her Serena Williams Fund, have collaborated with organizations in developing nations to use sports development to improve the quality of life for their citizens. Other notable figures include Muhammad Ali, who championed peace and education initiatives in Africa; David Beckham, who works with UNICEF to enhance health and education for children; and Yao Ming, who promotes basketball and supports educational initiatives in various countries. These icons leverage their influence to inspire change and demonstrate the power of sports as a tool for social development.

Shirotriya (2018), stated that sport icons have established sports academies in their home states, and encouraged a good level of commitment among partners to prepare players in their academy. According to Ananomo and Agbanusi (2012), sport offers chances for cultural integration through inter-racial, inter-ethnic, and inter-generational cultural exchanges. The world comes together through sports. Even sworn adversaries admire it and respond with such intensity. For example, it is uncommon for North and South

Korean government figures to get together and hold substantive talks outside of a sporting event; likewise, lateral contact between Israelis and Palestinians is more likely to happen on the football field than in a boardroom (Onifade, 2021). Also, sport serves as a unifying element among society's members. Despite their strong animosity for one another stemming from ethnic and religious prejudice, Nigerians appear to have a fondness for sport. Regularly during sport programmes, they put aside their political, religious, and ethnic prejudices to support their country's teams at international tournaments (Onifade & Adeyinka, 2020).

Well documented evidence show that sports may hold the key to improved social inclusion and address a range of economic, social, and environmental issues (European Commission, 2018; Jane & Gibson, 2017; Powell, 2015; 2018). Sports also have the power to unite people and communities while advancing social causes including social development, health, education, and climate change (Koutrou & Kohe, 2021). Grassroots sports, defined as sports activities organized at the community level and involving diverse participants ranging from children to amateur athletes, are used in identifying and nurturing future champions. These programmes do not only encourage physical activity and healthy lifestyles but also provide a pathway for aspiring athletes to advance to elite levels of competition. Despite the intrinsic value of grassroots sports, states and the nation at large encounter several barriers that impede its development.

Infrastructure limitations present a primary challenge across many communities in Delta State. Inadequacy and poor maintenance of sports facilities, including fields and gyms, restrict access and quality of training opportunities for athletes. Moreover, the scarcity of modern sports equipment and professional coaching further diminishes the effectiveness of talent development initiatives. Financial constraints exacerbate these challenges, as limited funding from government bodies, private sectors, and local initiatives constrain the expansion and sustainability of grassroots sports programmes. This financial scarcity does not only affect the infrastructure and equipment but also limits access to essential support services such as sports psychology, physiotherapy, and nutrition counseling, needed for a holistic athlete development. Psychological preparation is a key component of grassroots sports programmes, designed to enhance athletes' mental resilience, focus, and performance. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of these psychological preparation modules in achieving goals has not been thoroughly evaluated. This lack of assessment creates uncertainty about whether these modules are effectively addressing the needs of young athletes and contributing to their overall development.

Various organizations within Nigeria have also taken steps to enhance grassroots sports development. For instance, the Nigerian Football Federation (NFF) has implemented youth leagues that provide competitive opportunities for young footballers across different regions (NFF Annual Report, 2021). Despite these efforts, several challenges persist in Nigeria's grassroots sports landscape. Issues such as corruption within sporting federations, lack of adequate facilities, and limited access to quality coaching remain significant barriers (Adeleke, Olawale, & Ige, 2022). Furthermore, socio-economic factors often influence participation rates; many youths may prioritize employment or education over engaging in sports due to financial constraints. Owoeye et al. (2021) opined that Nigerian youth athletes who engaged in structured mental training exhibited enhanced focus during competitions compared to those who did not participate in such programmes.

Understanding the impact of psychological preparation modules is essential for optimizing grassroots sports programmes. Psychological readiness, encompassing motivation, focus, stress management, and confidence, is necessary for optimal athletic performance (Reyes-Bossio, et al., 2022). Without effective psychological preparation, athletes may struggle to reach their full potential, experience increased anxiety and stress, and face difficulties in maintaining motivation and resilience.

Statement of the Problem

Sports participation at all levels has some recognized benefits such as improved physical health, social cohesion, and personal growth. This is why sports development is important at all levels of the society, including the grassroots. Research, however, indicates that psychological readiness encompassing motivation, focus, stress management and confidence are necessary for optimal athletic performance

(Reyes-Bossio et al., 2022). Without effective psychological preparation, athletes may struggle to reach their full potential, experience increased anxiety and stress, and face difficulties in maintaining motivation and resilience (Owoeye et al., 2021).

The development of sports at the grassroots is often obstructed by a lack of effective psychological preparation modules for young athletes, and this compromises their mental resilience and performance. Despite the documented benefits of mental training, structured psychological interventions are still absent in many grassroots contexts. Studies show that athletes who engage in mental training exhibit enhanced focus and reduced anxiety (Owoeye et al., 2021), reinforcing the urgency for grassroots-specific psychological modules.

The challenges facing grassroots sports resonate deeply with the researcher, whose commitment to improving the lives of young athletes is rooted in personal experiences. Witnessing the untapped potential of youth athletes and a lack of sufficient training for athletes, especially in Delta State, using sport psychological preparation modules motivates this investigation. Arising from this problem, the study, therefore, aims to explore the impact of sport psychological preparation techniques such as mindfulness, goal-setting, and emotional regulation on grassroots sports development in Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the impact of goal setting on grassroots sports development in Delta State?
2. What is the impact of stress management and relaxation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State?
3. What is the impact of focus and concentration training on grassroots sports development in Delta State?
4. What is the impact of motivation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State?
5. What is the impact of emotional regulation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State?
6. What is the impact of confidence building techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were raised and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study.

1. There is no significant relationship between goal setting and grassroots sports development in Delta State.
2. There is no significant relationship between Stress management and relaxation techniques and grassroots sports development in Delta State.
3. Focus and concentration training have no significant relationship with grassroots sports development in Delta State.
4. Motivation techniques have no significant relationship with grassroots sports development in Delta State.
5. Emotional regulation techniques have no significant relationship with grassroots sports development in Delta State.
6. Confidence-building techniques have no significant relationship with grassroots sports development in Delta State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to evaluate the impact of the psychological preparation module on grassroots sports development in Delta State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objective of this study would be to;

1. Determine the impact of goal setting on grassroots sports development in Delta State.
2. Determine the impact of stress management and relaxation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State.
3. Investigate the impact of focus and concentration training on grassroots sports development in Delta State.
4. Evaluate the impact of motivation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State.

5. Investigate the impact of emotional regulation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State.
6. Examine the impact of confidence building techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Under this sub-heading, the following would be looked at: goal setting in sports development, stress management and relaxation techniques in sport development, focus and concentration training, motivation techniques, emotional regulation, confidence building and grassroots sports development in Nigeria.

The Concept of Sports Psychological Preparation Module

A sports psychological preparation module (SPPM) also termed Psychological Skills Training (PST) programme, mental skills training package, or structured mental training intervention is a theoretically grounded, systematically structured, periodised, and evaluable intervention comprising multiple evidence-based psychological techniques delivered across several sessions with the explicit aim of developing, refining, and automating mental skills that enhance competitive performance and psychological well-being (Vealey, 2007; Birrer & Morgan, 2010; Brown & Fletcher, 2017; Gucciardi et al., 2022).

An SPPM, which usually lasts six to sixteen weeks, differs from informal mental coaching or isolated single-technique interventions in that it is modular, progressive, multimodal, individualized, and ecologically valid (Dosil, 2006; Weinberg & Gould, 2019).

Sport psychology transitioned from descriptive research to applied intervention science in the late 1970s and early 1980s, giving rise to the systematic training of psychological skills (Vealey, 1988; Weinberg & Gould, 2019). Suinn's (1972a, 1972b) visuo-motor behavior rehearsal, Ogilvie and Tutko's (1970) personality profiling, and Mahoney and Avenier's (1977) identification of Olympic gymnasts' psychological traits are examples of groundbreaking contributions. Vealey (1988) developed the first formal multi-component "psychological skills training package," and during the 1990s and 2000s, the term "sports psychological preparation module" became popular in Latin American and European scholarship (Dosil, 2006; Roffé, 2001).

Contemporary SPPM design is underpinned by four dominant models:

1. Individual Zones of Optimal Functioning (IZOF) Model (Hanin, 2000, 2010)
2. Multidimensional Anxiety Theory and Catastrophe Model (Hardy, 1990; Hardy et al., 1996)
3. Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Ryan & Deci, 2017)
4. Cognitive-behavioural and social-cognitive theories (Bandura, 1997; Meichenbaum, 1977)

Applied sport psychology has converged on a core set of evidence-based techniques that form the backbone of almost every effective Psychological Skills Training (PST) or Sport Psychology Mental Performance (SPPM) programme. Meta-analyses and expert consensus statements consistently identify the following eight "canonical" techniques as appearing in more than 85 % of published, successful interventions (Brown & Fletcher, 2017; Lochbaum et al., 2021; Schneider et al., 2023; Latinjak et al., 2024):

1. Goal setting
2. Imagery/mental rehearsal
3. Self-talk/cognitive restructuring
4. Arousal regulation (relaxation & activation)
5. Concentration and attentional control
6. Pre-performance and performance routines
7. Confidence and self-efficacy enhancement

The variables of sports psychological preparation modules used in this study are explained below:

Focus and concentration: This is the ability to maintain attention on a task while filtering out distractions. These are essential components of athletic performance, particularly at the grassroots level where young athletes are developing their skills (Weinberg & Gould, 2018). The ability to maintain attention on a task

while filtering out distractions can significantly be a pointer to performance outcomes. Research indicates that mental training is as important as physical training in sports (Weinberg & Gould, 2018). For instance, mindfulness practices have been shown to improve concentration levels and reduce anxiety in competitive environments (Kabat-Zinn, 1990); thus athletes with better concentration skills tend to perform better under pressure (Weinberg & Gould, 2018).

Motivation: Motivation can be defined as internal and external factors that stimulate desire and energy in individuals to be continually interested and committed to a task, role, or subject (Ryan & Deci, 2017). It encompasses the biological, emotional, social, and cognitive forces that activate behavior. In sports development, motivation is a major tool as it influences participation levels, performance outcomes, and engagement in physical activities. According to Deci and Ryan (2020), motivation can be categorized into intrinsic and extrinsic types. Intrinsic motivation refers to engaging in an activity for its inherent satisfaction or pleasure, while extrinsic motivation involves performing an activity to achieve some separable outcome. Utilizing these motivational types is essential for developing effective grassroots sports programmes that cater to diverse participant needs. Ojo (2021) opined: motivational techniques such as goal setting, positive reinforcement, and creating supportive environments are essential for fostering youth participation in sports.

Emotional regulation: This refers to the processes by which individuals influence their emotions, when they experience them, and how they express them. Gross (2015) reiterated: emotional regulation encompasses a range of strategies that individuals use to manage their emotional experiences effectively. This includes both the enhancement of positive emotions and the suppression or modulation of negative emotions, he retorted. In sports, emotional regulation is need as athletes often face high-pressure situations that can provoke intense emotional responses. In grassroots sports development, these techniques can be integrated into training programmes. For example, mindfulness-based interventions have shown promise in enhancing athletes' focus and reducing performance anxiety (Birrer & Morgan, 2010; Niven, 2017).

Influenced by four sources: mastery experiences Confidence building: Confidence building is the process of enhancing an individual's belief in their own abilities and potentials. Bandura (2014), stated that confidence is primarily , vicarious experiences, verbal persuasion and emotional states. According to him, mastery experiences involve successfully completing tasks that enhance self-efficacy; vicarious experiences occur when individuals observe others succeeding; verbal persuasion includes encouragement from others; and emotional states pertain to how individuals interpret their feelings during performance situations,

Goal setting: Goal setting refers to the process of establishing specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) objectives that guide individuals, teams, or organizations toward achieving desired outcomes. Goal setting is a fundamental component of sports development, particularly at the grassroots level, where it plays a vital role in shaping the future of athletes, teams, and organizations (Oduor et al., 2022). The process of establishing SMART objectives guides athletes, coaches, and organizations toward achieving desired outcomes, such as improved performance, increased participation, and enhanced overall well-being (Muli et al., 2023).

Stress Management: Stress management is a wide range of practices, methods and approaches that can help individuals cope with and reduce their stress. Some of these includes therapy, medication, and sporting activities.

Sports development

Sports development refers to a strategic process aimed at improving and expanding sports activities in order to enhance the overall quality of life, promote social well-being, and contribute to national or regional economic growth. It involves both the growth of participation in sports across all levels, as well as the development of the infrastructure, policies, and institutional support needed to sustain and improve sports practices over time (Efebeh, 2020). The concept encompasses several core dimensions like participation which involves encouraging more people to engage in sports, from grassroots to elite levels, performance which also involve enhancing the performance of athletes through improved training,

facilities, and support systems, Coaching and Education that is also concerned with developing skilled coaches and sports professionals who can mentor athletes and help build the next generation of sports talent (Deemua, 2019). Infrastructure which is needed in creating and maintaining sports facilities, providing the necessary equipment, and ensuring access to sports resources. Policy and Governance that is critical as it is needed in formulating and implementing policies that ensure sports are developed in a fair, inclusive, and sustainable way (Deemua, 2019; Awoyinfa, et al. 2019; Orji, at al. 2022).

Dimensions of Sports Development: Sports can serve as a medium for unifying people across ethnic, cultural, and religious lines as observed by Efebeh's (2020) that in Nigeria, sports can break down barriers, particularly during national or international sporting events. The collective experience of supporting a national team or participating in sports can foster a sense of unity and pride. In this sense, sports development is not only about improving individual or team performance but also about fostering social cohesion and collective identity. At the grassroots level, sports development often focuses on youth engagement, providing young people with positive outlets for their energy and helping them develop key life skills.

Goal setting in Sports Development

Effective goal setting facilitates a sense of direction, motivation, and focus, enabling individuals and teams to work towards common objectives and strive for excellence (Chikanda & Chikoko, 2021). In the context of grassroots sports development, goal setting is essential for creating a supportive environment that fosters growth, development, and success (Ndlovu, Khumalo, & Dube, 2020). By setting clear and achievable goals, sports organizations can promote a culture of excellence, encourage participation, and develop talented athletes who can compete at the highest levels (Afolabi et al., 2022).

Importance of Goal Setting in Grassroots Sports: Goal setting is important in sports development for these reasons.

In relation to grassroots sports development, confidence building techniques can empower athletes - especially youth - to engage in sports activities with a positive mindset. These techniques can include goal setting, positive reinforcement, skill development workshops, and mentorship programmes (Smith & Smoll, 2016). Such strategies do not only promote individual confidence but also contribute to a supportive community environment that encourages participation (Weiss & Chaumeton 2014). The integration of confidence-building techniques within grassroots sports programmes has been shown to yield significant benefits. It is indicated that when young athletes receive constructive feedback and encouragement from coaches and peers, they are more likely to develop resilience and a positive self-image (Smith et al., 2018). This does not only enhances their performance but also increases retention rates in sports programmes they retorted.

Figure: 2.1 Author’s Conceptual Framework

Psychological Preparation Module: encompasses various techniques like goal setting, stress management, focus and concentration training, motivation techniques, emotional regulation, and confidence-building.

Performance of Grassroots Athletes: Is the mediating variable, which is influenced by the psychological preparation techniques and directly impacts grassroots sports development.

Grassroots Sports Development: is the dependent variable, representing the overall improvement and growth of sports activities at the community level.

Arrows: The arrows indicate the direction of influence or causal relationships between the variables. For example, the arrow from the psychological preparation module to the performance of grassroots athletes shows that the former affects the latter. Similarly, the arrow from the performance of grassroots athletes to grassroots sports development shows that improved performance leads to better sports development.

Theoretical Review

For this study, several theories can explain the dynamics of sport psychological preparation module and grassroots sports development. These include Achievement Goal Theory by Nicholls (1984), Self-Determination Theory by Deci & Ryan (1985), Cognitive Behavioral Theory by Beck (1976), Social Learning Theory by Bandura (1977), and the Theory of Planned Behavior by Ajzen (1991). For this study, two theories were adopted to explain

the dynamics of psychological preparation modules and grassroots sports development. These are the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) by Deci and Ryan (1985) and the Achievement Goal Theory (AGT) by

Nicholls (1984). Each provided a foundation into an understanding of athlete motivation, psychological resilience, and performance outcomes, especially in a grassroots environment.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted a correlational research design to examine the Impact of Sport Psychological Preparation Modules on Grassroots Sports Development. This design enabled the researcher to systematically investigate the strength of relationships between the psychological preparation variables and grassroots sports outcomes without manipulating the variables. The use of structured questionnaires facilitated standardized data collection, ensuring consistency, reliability, and ease of analysis across the study population.

Population of the Study

Asika (2012) noted that a population comprises all potential components, subjects, or observations connected to a specific phenomenon of interest. For this study, the population is 2,743, comprising 2,344 athletes, 322 coaches and trainers and 77 Sports Administrators (Delta State Sports Commission, 2023).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

From a total population of 2,743, Taro Yamane's formula was used to calculate the minimum sample size of 349 for the study. The calculation is below:

$$n = \frac{N}{11 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

- N=2743 (total population of Participants),
- e=0.05 (margin of error of 5%).

$$n = \frac{2743}{1 + 2743(0.0025)} = \frac{2743}{1 + 6.8575} = \frac{2743}{7.8575} = 349 \text{ as the sample size.}$$

Thereafter, a multi-stage sampling technique was employed to obtain a comprehensive and representative sample of grassroots sports stakeholders across the state. In the first stage, Delta State was divided into its three senatorial districts: Delta North, Delta Central, and Delta South. This geographical division allowed the study to reflect regional diversity. In the second stage, purposive sampling was used to select specific sports facilities and programmes within each district. This involved identifying well-established centres that actively promote and participate in grassroots sports development. In Delta North, selected facilities included the Stephen Keshi Stadium (Asaba), Agbor Township Stadium, and the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba Sports Complex. For Delta Central, facilities such as Sapele Stadium, Ughelli Township Stadium, and Jesse Township Stadium were chosen. In Delta South, Warri Township Stadium, Oleh Township Stadium, and Otu-Jeremi Township Stadium were selected. Stratified random sampling was then applied to select participants from various sports disciplines roles (athletes, coaches, and administrators) ensuring balanced representation. The sample was proportionally stratified based on the population distribution within each district and the range of sports disciplines represented in each facility.

Table 3.1: Final Table Based on Total Population of 2,743 and Sample Size of 349

Group	Population	% of Total	Sample Size
Athletes	2,344	85.45	298
Coaches & Trainers	322	11.74	41
Sports Administrators	77	2.81	10
Total	2,743	100	349

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled “Sports Psychological Preparation Module and Grassroots Sports Development Questionnaire (SPPMGSDQ)”. The questionnaire was developed by the researcher based on a comprehensive review of literature, the research objectives, and the study variables. The instrument consisted of two main sections: Section A and Section B.

Section A focused on the demographic characteristics of the respondents, including age, gender, role (athlete, coach/trainer, or sports administrator), senatorial district, and sports discipline.

Section B was designed to capture data related to the core variables of the study, and it was organized according to the research questions. This section was divided into seven thematic sub-sections, each representing a variable in the study: Goal Setting Techniques, Stress Management and Relaxation Techniques, Focus and Concentration Training, Motivation Techniques, Emotional Regulation Techniques, Confidence-Building Techniques, Grassroots Sports Development (the dependent variable).

Each item in Section B was measured using a four-point Likert scale to assess respondents’ level of agreement with each statement. The scale was structured as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. Respondents were instructed to select the option that best represented their level of agreement with each statement. The use of the Likert scale allowed for standardized quantifiable measurement of attitudes and perceptions relating to the psychological preparation modules and grassroots sports development. The questionnaire was reviewed by experts in sport psychology and educational measurement to ensure its validity, and a pilot test was conducted to determine its reliability.

Validity of the Instrument

The validity of the research instrument was assessed through scrutiny by the researchers’ supervisor and two other experts from the Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education. Each expert was asked to evaluate the adequacy of the items on the instrument. They reviewed the content to determine whether the items adequately sample the subject matter of the variables under study. In Addition, they assessed the instrument for its face and content validity. Based on their feedback, corrections and suggestions, the final version of the questionnaire was produced.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the research instrument was determined using the Cronbach Alpha method of internal consistency. This method assesses the reliability of a set of scale or test items. A pilot test was administered to respondents outside the study area, and the responses from the questionnaire was analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha. The analysis was conducted for each variable separately, as well as for the entire instrument which yielded Cronbach's Alpha 0.81 result.

Method of Data Collection

Data collection involved administering structured questionnaires to athletes, coaches, and administrators to gather quantitative data on both the independent and dependent variables. The questionnaire included sections on psychological preparation (independent variable) and grassroots sports development (dependent variable). This simultaneous collection ensured a comprehensive understanding of the relationships between the variables. The data collection process involved the researcher and two research assistants to ensure efficient and thorough data gathering. All data collection activities was conducted in compliance with ethical standards, ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of participants. A total of 349 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. Out of these, 340 questionnaires were successfully retrieved and deemed usable for analysis. This represents a retrieval rate of approximately 97.4%. Consequently, 9 questionnaires were either lost or incomplete, accounting for a non-response rate of about 2.6%.

Data collection and fieldwork were carried out between July 2024 and March 2025. The study investigated how these psychological strategies impact athletes’ performance, participation, and mental resilience at the grassroots level within the defined time frame.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the questionnaire was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 27). Demographic (Personal Variable) was analyzed using frequencies and percentages to provide an overview of the respondents' characteristics. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), was used to analyze the research questions related to grassroots sports development. This analysis helped identify trends and patterns in the data. (e.g., goal setting, stress management, focus training) and grassroots sports development. In addition, regression analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between these variables of sport psychological preparation module and grassroots sports development. All null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter contains the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data collected from the sample respondents through the use of questionnaire. The presentation was done in different sections.

Demographics (Personal Variables).

The demographic (Personal Variables) considered in this study include the educational level of the respondents, their age range, sex, years of experience in sports, sports category, type of sport, and the organization they belong to. The researcher aimed to capture a broad range of respondents from different educational backgrounds, age groups, and sporting experiences to ensure a comprehensive representation of the target population. Below is the presentation of each demographic characteristic.

Table 4.1.1: Level of Education of Respondents

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Secondary	102	30.0
Tertiary	151	44.4
Professional	87	25.6
Total	340	100

The results, as shown in Table 4.1.1, reveal that 44.4% of the respondents had tertiary education, followed by 30% who had secondary education. The remaining 25.6% of respondents were professionals. This suggests a higher proportion of respondents with tertiary education.

Table 4. 1.2: Age of Respondents

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Under 15-20 years	87	25.6
26–30 years	151	44.4
31–35 years	64	18.8
36–40 years	38	11.2
Total	340	100

As shown in Table 4.1.2, the largest group of respondents, 44.4%, fell within the 26–30 years' age range. This was followed by 25.6% of respondents in the 15-20 years' category. Only 18.8% were aged between 31-35 years, and the smallest group, 11.2%, were aged between 36-40 years. The distribution is presented below:

Table 4.1. 3: Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	189	55.6
Female	151	44.4
Total	340	100

As presented in Table 4.1.3, 55.6% of the respondents were male, while 44.4% were female. This shows a slightly higher proportion of male respondents.

Table 4.1.4: Experience of Respondents

Years of Experience	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-5 years	113	33.2
6-10 years	76	22.4
11-15 years	125	36.8
20-25 years	26	7.6
Total	340	100

As shown in Table 4.1.4, the largest group of respondents, 36.8%, had 11-15 years of experience. This was followed by 33.2% who had 1-5 years of experience. The smallest group, 7.6%, had 20-25 years of experience in sports.

Table 4.1.5: Sports Category of Respondents

Sports Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Grassroot Athlete	291	85.6
Coach and Trainer	39	11.5
Administrator	10	2.9
Total	340	100

As shown in Table 4.1.5, a large majority of respondents, 85.6%, were grassroots athletes. This was followed by 11.5% who were coaches and trainers, and only 2.9% were administrators.

Table 4.1.6: Type of Sport Played by Respondents

Type of Sport	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Football	113	33.2
Basketball	114	33.5
Athletics	75	22.1
Table Tennis	38	11.2
Total	340	100

As shown in Table 4.1.6, a large majority of respondents, 33.5%, plays basketball, 33.2% plays football, this was followed by 22.1% who were athletics, and only 11.2% were table tennis players.

Table 4.1.7: Sport Organization Respondents Belong To

Sport Organization	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Government	151	44.4
Private Sports Club	76	22.4
Educational Institution	113	33.2
Total	340	100

As shown in Table 4.1.7, 44.4% of the respondents belonged to government organizations, while 33.2% were part of educational institutions. The smallest group, 22.4%, belonged to private sports clubs.

4.2 Test of Research Questions

Research Question One: *What is the impact of goal setting on grassroots sports development in Delta State?*

A Pearson correlation was conducted to examine the relationship between Goal Setting and Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) in Delta State. The results are summarized below:

Table 4.2.1: Summary of Research Question One Results

Research Question	Correlation (Pearson)	Sig. (2-tailed)
RQ1: Goal Setting ↔ Grassroots Sports Development	0.745	0.000

Note: $p < 0.01$.

As shown in Table 4.2.1, the Pearson correlation between Goal Setting and Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) is 0.745 ($p = 0.000$), with a two-tailed significance level of 0.000. This correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. This indicates a strong positive relationship between goal setting and grassroots sports development in Delta State, suggesting that effective goal setting is a key factor influencing the development and growth of grassroots sports programmes in the area under study.

Research Question Two: *What is the impact of stress management and relaxation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State?*

A Pearson correlation was conducted to examine the relationship between Stress Management and Relaxation Techniques and Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) in Delta State. The results are summarized below:

Table 4.2.2: Summary of Research Question Two Results

Research Question	Correlation (Pearson)	Sig. (2-tailed)
RQ2: Stress Management and Relaxation Techniques ↔ Grassroots Sports Development	0.997	0.000

Note: $p < 0.01$.

As shown in Table 4.2.2, the Pearson correlation between Stress Management and Relaxation Techniques and Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) is 0.997 ($p = 0.000$), with a two-tailed significance level of 0.000. This correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. This indicates a very strong positive relationship between stress management and relaxation techniques and grassroots sports development, suggesting that as Proper management of stress and its implementation increases, Grassroots Sports Development increase signaling an enhancement of grassroots sports programmes in the state.

Research Question Three: *What is the impact of focus and concentration training on grassroots sports development in Delta State?*

A Pearson correlation was conducted to examine the relationship between Focus and Concentration Training and Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) in Delta State. The results are summarized below:

Table 4.2.3: Summary of Research Question Three Results

Research Question	Correlation (Pearson)	Sig. (2-tailed)
RQ3: Focus and Concentration Training ↔ Grassroots Sports Development	0.985	0.000

Note: $p < 0.01$.

As shown in Table 4.2.3, the Pearson correlation between Focus and Concentration Training and Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) is 0.985 ($p = 0.000$), with a two-tailed significance level of 0.000. This correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. This indicates a very strong positive relationship between focus and concentration training and grassroots sports development, suggesting that the implementation of focus and concentration techniques leads to a notable enhancement in the development of grassroots sports programmes in Delta State.

Research Question Four: *What is the impact of motivation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State?*

A Pearson correlation was conducted to examine the relationship between Motivation Techniques and Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) in Delta State. The results are summarized below:

Table 4.2.4: Summary of Research Question Four Results

Research Question	Correlation (Pearson)	Sig. (2-tailed)
RQ4: Motivation Techniques ↔ Grassroots Sports Development	0.976	0.000

Note: $p < 0.01$.

As shown in Table 4.2.4, the Pearson correlation between Motivation Techniques and Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) is 0.976 ($p = 0.000$), with a two-tailed significance level of 0.000. This correlation is

statistically significant at the 0.01 level. This indicates a very strong positive relationship between motivation techniques and grassroots sports development, the result also suggests that as motivation techniques are enhanced and implemented, grassroots sports development in the study area tends to also significantly improved.

Research Question Five: *What is the impact of emotional regulation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State?*

A Pearson correlation was conducted to examine the relationship between Emotional Regulation Techniques and Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) in Delta State. The results are summarized below:

Table 4.2.5: Summary of Research Question Five Results

Research Question	Correlation (Pearson)	Sig. (2-tailed)
RQ5: Emotional Regulation Techniques ↔ Grassroots Sports Development	0.945	0.000

Note: $p < 0.01$.

As shown in Table 4.2.5, the Pearson correlation between Emotional Regulation Techniques and Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) is 0.945 ($p = 0.000$), with a two-tailed significance level of 0.000. This correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. This indicates a very strong positive relationship between emotional regulation techniques and grassroots sports development, suggesting that effective emotional regulation increases, it also significantly enhance the development of grassroots sports programmes in Delta State.

Research Question Six: *What is the impact of confidence building techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State?*

A Pearson correlation was conducted to examine the relationship between Confidence Building Techniques and Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) in Delta State. The results are summarized below:

Table 4.2.6: Summary of Research Question Six Results

Research Question	Correlation (Pearson)	Sig. (2-tailed)
RQ6: Confidence Building Techniques ↔ Grassroots Sports Development	0.839	0.000

Note: $p < 0.01$.

As shown in Table 4.2.6, the Pearson correlation between Confidence Building Techniques and Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) is 0.839 ($p = 0.000$), with a two-tailed significance level of 0.000. The correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. This indicates a strong positive relationship between confidence building techniques and grassroots sports development, suggesting that as confidence building increases and enhanced, the growth and progress of grassroots sports programmes in the study area tends to also increase.

4.3 Test of Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis One (H01): There is no significant relationship between goal setting and grassroots sports development in Delta State.

A Linear Regression analysis was conducted to test Hypothesis One which states, "There is no significant relationship between goal setting and grassroots sports development in Delta State." The results are summarized below:

Table 4.3.1: Regression of Goal Setting and Grassroots Sports Development

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta		H ₀₁
1	(Constant)	7.647	0.483		Rejected
	Goal-Setting	0.589	0.029	0.745	

a. Dependent Variable: Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) scale

From the regression result as seen in the Coefficients table and summarized in (Table 4.3.1) above, the unstandardized coefficient (B) for Goal Setting is 0.589, with a p-value of 0.000, which is well below the 0.01 significance threshold. This indicates that there is a significantly positive relationship between goal setting and grassroots sports development in Delta State. The positive coefficient suggests that as goal setting increases, grassroots sports development also increases. The t-value for goal setting is 20.559, which is highly significant and further supports the conclusion that goal setting has a substantial effect on grassroots sports development. With a p-value of 0.000, we reject the null hypothesis (H₀1) and conclude that there is a significant relationship between goal setting and grassroots sports development in Delta State.

Hypothesis Two (H02): There is no significant effect of Stress management and relaxation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State.

A Linear Regression analysis was conducted to test Hypothesis Two, which states, "There is no significant effect of Stress management and relaxation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State." The results are summarized below:

Table 4.3.2: Regression of Stress Management and Relaxation Techniques on Grassroots Sports Development

Mode	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
1	B	Std. Error	Beta						
1	(Constant)	0.090	0.076	1.183	0.238	0.997	0.994	0.994	H ₀ 2 Rejected
	Stress Management_ Relaxation	0.994	0.004	0.997	231.111	0.000			

a. Dependent Variable: Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) scale

From the regression result as seen in the Coefficients table and summarized in (Table 4.3.2) above, the unstandardized coefficient (B) for Stress Management and Relaxation Techniques is 0.994, with a p-value of 0.000, which is well below the 0.01 significance threshold. This indicates that there is a significantly positive relationship between stress management and relaxation techniques and grassroots sports development in Delta State. The positive coefficient suggests that as the implementation of stress management and relaxation techniques increases, grassroots sports development also increases. Also, the Model Summary shows an R value of 0.997 and an R² value of 0.994, indicating that the model explains 99.4% of the variance in grassroots sports development. The ANOVA table also shows a very significant F-statistic of 53412.332 with a p-value of 0.000, confirming the overall model fit. The t-value for stress management and relaxation techniques is 231.111, which is highly significant and further supports the conclusion that these techniques have a substantial effect on grassroots sports development. With a p-value of 0.000, we reject the null hypothesis (H₀2) and conclude that stress management and relaxation techniques significantly influence grassroots sports development in Delta State.

Hypothesis Three (H03): Focus and concentration training have no significant relationship with grassroots sports development in Delta State.

A Linear Regression analysis was conducted to test Hypothesis Three, which states, "Focus and concentration training have no significant relationship with grassroots sports development in Delta State." The results are summarized below:

Table 4.3.3: Regression of Focus and Concentration Training on Grassroots Sports Development

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta						
1	(Constant)	0.506	0.161	3.139	0.002	0.985	0.971	0.971	H ₀₃ Rejected
	Focus_and_Concentration	0.973	0.009	0.985	105.976	0.000			

a. Dependent Variable: Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) scale

From the regression result as seen in the Coefficients table and summarized in (Table 4.3.3) above, the unstandardized coefficient (B) for Focus and Concentration Training is 0.973, with a p-value of 0.000, which is well below the 0.01 significance threshold. This indicates that there is a significantly positive relationship between focus and concentration training and grassroots sports development in Delta State. The positive coefficient suggests that as focus and concentration training increases, grassroots sports development also increases. Furthermore, the Model Summary shows an R value of 0.985 and an R² value of 0.971, indicating that the model explains 97.1% of the variance in grassroots sports development. The ANOVA table also shows a very significant F-statistic of 11230.872 with a p-value of 0.000, confirming the overall model fit. The t-value for focus and concentration training is 105.976, which is highly significant and further supports the conclusion that these techniques have a substantial effect on grassroots sports development. With a p-value of 0.000, we reject the null hypothesis (H₀₃) and conclude that focus and concentration training significantly influence grassroots sports development in Delta State.

Hypothesis Four (H₀₄): Motivation techniques have no significant relationship with grassroots sports development in Delta State.

A Linear Regression analysis was conducted to test Hypothesis Four, which states, "Motivation techniques have no significant effect on grassroots sports development in Delta State." The results are summarized below:

Table 4.3.4: Regression of Motivation Techniques on Grassroots Sports Development

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta						
1	(Constant)	0.922	0.201	4.595	0.000	0.976	0.953	0.953	H ₀₄ Rejected
	Motivation Techniques	0.951	0.011	0.976	83.014	0.000			

a Dependent Variable: Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) scale

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	750.160	1	750.160	6891.364	.000 ^b
	Residual	36.793	338	.109		
	Total	786.953	339			

a. Dependent Variable: Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) scale

b. Predictors: (Constant), Motivation Techniques

From the regression result as seen in the Coefficients table and summarized in (Table 4.3.4) above, the unstandardized coefficient (B) for Motivation Techniques is 0.951, with a p-value of 0.000, which is well below the 0.01 significance threshold. This indicates that there is a significant positive relationship between motivation techniques and grassroots sports development in Delta State. The positive coefficient suggests that as motivation techniques increase, grassroots sports development also increases. Moreover, the Model Summary shows an R value of 0.976 and an R² value of 0.953, indicating that the model explains 95.3% of the variance in grassroots sports development. The ANOVA table also shows a very significant F-statistic of 6891.364 with a p-value of 0.000, confirming the overall model fit. The t-value for motivation techniques is 83.014, which is highly significant and further supports the conclusion that these techniques have a substantial effect on grassroots sports development. With a p-value of 0.000, we reject the null hypothesis (H04) and conclude that motivation techniques significantly influence grassroots sports development in Delta State.

Hypothesis Five (H05): Emotional regulation techniques have no significant relationship with grassroots sports development in Delta State.

A Linear Regression analysis was conducted to test Hypothesis Five, which states, "Emotional regulation techniques would have no significant relationship with grassroots sports development in Delta State." The results are summarized below:

Table 4.3.5: Regression of Emotional Regulation Techniques on Grassroots Sports Development

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta						
1	(Constant)	1.985	0.295	6.740	0.000	0.945	0.892	0.892	H ₀₅ Rejected
	Emotional_Regulation	0.893	0.017	0.945	52.933	0.000			

a Dependent Variable: Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) scale

From the regression result as seen in the Coefficients table and summarized in (Table 4.3.5) above, the unstandardized coefficient (B) for Emotional Regulation is 0.893, with a p-value of 0.000, which is well below the 0.01 significance threshold. This indicates that there is a significant positive relationship between emotional regulation techniques and grassroots sports development in Delta State. The positive coefficient suggests that as emotional regulation techniques increase, grassroots sports development also increases. Also, the Model Summary shows an R value of 0.945 and an R² value of 0.892, indicating that the model explains 89.2% of the variance in grassroots sports development. The ANOVA table also shows a very significant F-statistic of 2801.858 with a p-value of 0.000, confirming the overall model fit. The t-value for emotional regulation techniques is 52.933, which is highly significant and further supports the conclusion that these techniques have a substantial effect on grassroots sports development. With a p-value of 0.000, we reject the null hypothesis (H05) and conclude that emotional regulation techniques significantly influence grassroots sports development in Delta State.

Hypothesis Six (H06): Confidence building techniques have no significant relationship with grassroots sports development in Delta State.

A Linear Regression analysis was conducted to test Hypothesis Six, which states, "Confidence building techniques have no significant impact on grassroots sports development in Delta State." The results are summarized below:

Table 4.3.6: Regression of Confidence Building Techniques on Grassroots Sports Development

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta						
1	(Constant)	4.903	0.447	10.974	0.000	0.839	0.704	0.703	H ₀₆ Rejected
	Confidence_Building	0.738	0.026	0.839	28.363	0.000			

a. Dependent Variable: Grassroots Sports Development (GSD) scale

From the regression result as seen in the Coefficients' table and summarized in (Table 4.3.6) above, the unstandardized coefficient (B) for Confidence Building is 0.738, with a p-value of 0.000, which is well below the 0.01 significance threshold. This indicates that there is a significant positive relationship between confidence building techniques and grassroots sports development in Delta State. The positive coefficient suggests that as confidence building techniques increase, grassroots sports development also increases. Furthermore, the Model Summary shows an R value of 0.839 and an R² value of 0.704, indicating that the model explains 70.4% of the variance in grassroots sports development. The ANOVA table also shows a very significant F-statistic of 804.475 with a p-value of 0.000, confirming the overall model fit. The t-value for confidence building techniques is 28.363, which is highly significant and further supports the conclusion that these techniques have a substantial impact on grassroots sports development. With a p-value of 0.000, we reject the null hypothesis (H₀₆) and conclude that confidence building techniques significantly influence grassroots sports development in Delta State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study evaluates the impact of sport psychological preparation module on grassroots sports development in Delta State, Nigeria. To guide the study, six research questions and six hypotheses were formulated. The results of the analysis of research questions and hypothesis is discussed below:

The results of research question one which states "What is the impact of goal setting on grassroots sports development in Delta State, indicates a strong positive relationship between goal setting and grassroots sports development in Delta State, suggesting that effective goal setting is a key factor influencing the development and growth of grassroots sports programmes in the area under study.

Research question two is on the impact of stress management and relaxation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State. It indicates a very strong positive relationship between stress management and relaxation techniques and grassroots sports development, suggesting that as Proper management of stress and its implementation increases, Grassroots Sports Development increase signaling an enhancement of grassroots

Research question three examined the impact of focus and concentration training on grassroots sports development in Delta State. The result showed very strong positive relationship between focus and concentration training and grassroots sports development, suggesting that the implementation of focus and concentration techniques leads to a notable enhancement in the development of grassroots sports programmes in Delta State.

Research question four examined the impact of motivation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State. The result of the analysis indicates a very strong positive relationship between motivation techniques and grassroots sports development, the result also suggests that as motivation techniques are enhanced and implemented, grassroots sports development in the study area tends to also significantly improved.

Research question five examined the impact of emotional regulation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State. The result indicates a very strong positive relationship between emotional

regulation techniques and grassroots sports development, suggesting that effective emotional regulation increases, it also significantly enhance the development of grassroots sports programmes in Delta State.

The analysis of research question six indicates a strong positive relationship between confidence building techniques and grassroots sports development, suggesting that as confidence building increases and enhanced, the growth and progress of grassroots sports programmes in the study area tends to also increase.

The findings for Hypothesis One showed a significant relationship between goal setting and grassroots sports development in Delta State. The regression analysis revealed a coefficient (B) of 0.589 with a p-value of 0.000, which is below the 0.01 threshold. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{01}), indicating that goal setting positively influences grassroots sports development. This result supports the findings of Afolabi et al. (2018), who reported that athletes who applied structured goal-setting strategies performed better in grassroots sports. It also aligns with Ojo and Adeyemi (2019), who found that goal setting helped to improve youth participation by reducing barriers and increasing motivation. Similarly, Nwankwo et al. (2020) observed that goal setting helped young athletes improve their skills and created a more supportive environment with their coaches. Eze Nnaji & Obioma, (2021) also showed that teams with collective goals had better cohesion and performance. Bird et al. (2024) emphasized the need for athlete involvement in goal-setting, noting that collaboration makes the process more effective. This reflects the approach used in this study, where goal setting was part of a broader psychological preparation module. The findings are also in line with Okeke, Ifeanyi-Akpanisi, & Chukwuemeka (2022), who reported that goal setting improved athlete satisfaction and retention, and Ochor et al. (2024), who found that structured goal-setting training led to better football passing skills.

The findings for Hypothesis Two showed a significant relationship between stress management and relaxation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State. The regression analysis revealed a coefficient (B) of 0.994 with a p-value of 0.000, which is below the 0.01 threshold. The model also recorded a very high R^2 value of 0.994, indicating that these techniques explain 99.4% of the variance in grassroots sports development. As a result, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) was rejected. This result aligns with the findings of Uche, Chukwuemeka & Ifeoma (2020), who observed that while most coaches recognized the importance of stress management strategies, practical application during training was often lacking. The present study confirms that effective implementation of these techniques can significantly enhance sports development outcomes. Similarly, DeWolfe and Fawver (2021) reported that progressive muscle relaxation helped reduce anxiety and improve focus among youth soccer players. Rumbold, Fletcher and Daniels (2018) also found that cognitive restructuring and relaxation techniques improved athletes' stress management and performance. Ibe et al. (2021) noted that psychological preparation, including stress management, positively impacted athlete performance at the grassroots level. The present study builds on that by showing that stress management and relaxation techniques alone have a strong predictive effect on sports development. In line with this, Baltzell et al. (2020) found mindfulness-based interventions reduced stress and improved relaxation among collegiate athletes, supporting the broader application of such techniques in sports. Weinberg et al. (2017) also reported that athletes who practiced stress management performed more consistently and with lower stress levels. Further support comes from Kremer, Caraballo, & Goudeau (2019), who observed improved performance and reduced stress after relaxation interventions in youth sports. Cogan, Loughhead and Ginis (2022) confirmed through meta-analysis that stress reduction techniques have a positive impact on performance in grassroots sports

The findings for Hypothesis Three revealed a significant effect of focus and concentration training on grassroots sports development in Delta State. The regression analysis produced a coefficient (B) of 0.973 and a p-value of 0.000, which is below the 0.01 level. With an R^2 value of 0.971, the model explains 97.1% of the variance in grassroots sports development. Based on these results, the null hypothesis (H_{03}) was rejected. This finding aligns with the study by Hanton, Fletcher and Coughlan (2015), which showed that focus training helped reduce anxiety and improve performance in young athletes. Similarly, Gucciardi et al. (2016) found that concentration training enhanced athletes' resilience and helped them cope with pressure more effectively over time. The current result is also supported by Noroozi et al.

(2024), who demonstrated in their study that external and holistic focus improved performance in skill-based tasks. Their findings suggest that attention focus techniques can be beneficial even for novice athletes. Al-Azzawi, Ackartani & Chtero (2023) further confirmed a positive correlation between attention focus and basic skills like scoring and ball handling in futsal, supporting the idea that focused attention enhances performance in precision-based sports. Durand-Bush et al. (2022) emphasized the importance of mental performance competencies, including concentration, in athlete development. While their study focused on high-performance sports, the current research adapted these competencies to suit grassroots athletes. Also, in support of the result of this hypothesis is, Weinberg and Gould (2017) which showed that athletes who used focus strategies developed better skills and achieved improved performance outcomes, while Jones, Hanton & Connaughton (2014) reported that focus training increased resilience and helped athletes perform better under pressure.

The findings for Hypothesis Four revealed a significant relationship between motivation techniques and grassroots sports development in Delta State. The regression analysis produced a coefficient (B) of 0.951 and a p-value of 0.000, which is below the 0.01 level. With an R² value of 0.953, the model explains 95.3% of the variance in grassroots sports development. Based on these results, the null hypothesis (H04) was rejected. This finding aligns with the study by Odok, Osaji, and Dan (2024), which showed that intrinsic and extrinsic motivation significantly influenced sports participation among secondary school students. Similarly, Boniface et al. (2023) found that motivational allowances such as bonuses, scholarships, and medical support significantly impacted athletes' engagement in sports across different states in Nigeria. The current result is also supported by Bondoc (2023), who reported that varsity players showed high motivation levels toward community-based sports initiatives, and that such motivation enhanced their competence and social skills. Aznan et al. (2024) further confirmed that service quality positively influenced motivation to participate in sports, particularly among university students. Their findings suggest that supportive environments and well-managed facilities help foster consistent sports participation. Also in support of the result of this hypothesis is Fadare et al. (2024), whose study showed how grassroots football programmes helped build social skills and community trust, emphasizing the importance of motivation and engagement at early stages of athlete development. These findings are reinforced by Mack et al. (2020), who reported that motivational interviewing increased athlete readiness and supported psychological development. Ohuruogu, Ugwuanyi, and Ugwu (2016) also echoed similar result that psychological preparation, including motivation, plays a central role in athlete performance. Reyes-Bossio et al. (2022) also noted that motivational interventions improved mental skills and reduced stress among high-performance athletes, while Abrahamsen (2013) found that a mastery-oriented climate enhanced vitality through motivation and passion in youth football players. All these studies support the current finding that motivation techniques are ever needed for grassroots sports development and should be integrated into athlete development programmes in Delta State.

The findings for Hypothesis Five revealed a significant effect of emotional regulation techniques on grassroots sports development in Delta State. The regression analysis produced a coefficient (B) of 0.893 and a p-value of 0.000, which is below the 0.01 level. With an R² value of 0.892, the model explains 89.2% of the variance in grassroots sports development. Based on these results, the null hypothesis (H05) was rejected. This finding is consistent with the study by Gross and Thompson (2016), which found that athletes who applied emotional regulation strategies such as situation selection, cognitive change, and response modulation reported better focus, reduced anxiety, and improved performance under pressure. Similarly, Warfield et al. (2023) discovered that relaxation and imagery techniques helped NCAA athletes manage competitive stress and maintain composure, leading to improved emotional control and performance outcomes. The current result is also supported by Fominykh and Kornienko (2020), who showed that athletes with higher self-efficacy were more likely to use adaptive emotional regulation strategies like cognitive reappraisal, resulting in greater motivation and success in competitive environments. Braun and Tamminen (2019) further confirmed that coaches' use of interpersonal emotional regulation strategies such as emotional validation and encouragement enhanced athlete motivation and strengthened the coach-athlete relationship. Also in support of the result of this hypothesis

is Buchanan and Janelle (2022), who reported that regulating breathing frequency under emotional conditions positively influenced motor performance, suggesting that physiological aspects of emotion regulation can also enhance sports outcomes. Moore and Marin (2019) emphasized the importance of emotional acceptance in sport, arguing that athletes who engage with and manage emotions effectively are more resilient and perform better. Their approach to emotional openness supports the integration of emotion regulation training into grassroots sports development, which the current study has examined in detail. Collectively, these studies support the present finding that emotional regulation techniques are essential for building resilience, reducing performance anxiety, and enhancing development among grassroots athletes in Delta State.

The findings for Hypothesis Six revealed a significant relationship between confidence building techniques and grassroots sports development in Delta State. The regression analysis produced a coefficient (B) of 0.738 and a p-value of 0.000, which is below the 0.01 level. With an R² value of 0.704, the model explains 70.4% of the variance in grassroots sports development. Based on these results, the null hypothesis (H06) was rejected. This finding are supported by the study of Jeroh (2014), which confidence building is important in grassroots sports as a foundational platform for talent identification and athlete development in Nigeria. Similarly, Coalter (2013) found that grassroots sports participation significantly improved young athletes' confidence and social skills, supporting the idea that psychological empowerment is a key outcome of well-structured grassroots programmes. The current result is also supported by Darnell and Hayburst (2014), who reported that supportive environments and positive reinforcement boosted athletes' self-belief and personal development. Muaz (2022) further emphasized the potential of grassroots initiatives to foster confidence and participation among youth despite structural challenges, suggesting the need for deeper integration of psychological strategies. Also, in support of the result of this hypothesis is McGuire et al. (2025), whose evaluation of a positive youth development (PYD) program found improvements in self-confidence and connection among participants. González-Hernández et al. (2024) confirmed that self-confidence acts as a buffer against anxiety and perfectionism in young athletes, enhancing their performance. In addition, while Almeida, Machi-Junior & Pike (2018) showed that increased participation following sports mega-events led to enhanced confidence among young athletes. Finally, Chikanda, Mwale, and Phiri (2021) found that consistent participation in grassroots sports improved self-esteem across various African youth programmes. Collectively, these studies support the current finding that confidence building techniques is needed in the development of grassroots athletes.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that sport psychological preparation modules are essential elements in the growth and success of grassroots sports development in Delta State. From the research findings, all six constructs investigated —goal setting, stress management and relaxation, focus and concentration, motivation, emotional regulation, and confidence building exhibited strong or very strong positive correlations with sports development. Among them, stress management and focus training showed the highest influence. These findings showed an urgent need to integrate psychological support and training into grassroots sports programmes. With adequate mental preparedness, athletes are more equipped to face challenges, improve performance, and sustain long-term development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the research and further enhance grassroots sports development in Delta State, the following recommendations are proposed;

1. **Integrate Psychological Modules into Coaching Programmes:** Coaches and trainers should be trained in psychological preparation modules and incorporate them into regular athlete training routines.

2. **Government and Private Investment:** Investment in sports psychology services should be increased across all levels of grassroots sports, including hiring sports psychologists in sports academies.
3. **Workshops and Seminars:** Periodic mental training seminars and workshops should be organized to educate stakeholders on the benefits of psychological preparedness.
4. **Customized Goal Setting Programmes:** Structured goal-setting activities should be included in team planning to build cohesion and purpose.
5. **Stress Reduction Protocols:** Incorporate mindfulness, relaxation, and stress management activities into daily training to help athletes manage performance anxiety.
6. **Develop Mental Focus Curriculums:** Focus and concentration drills should be embedded in skill training, especially in sports requiring precision.
7. **Recognition and Rewards Systems:** Use motivational tools like recognition, scholarships, and competition exposure to build intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.
8. **Emotional Intelligence Training:** Train athletes and coaches in emotional regulation strategies to improve responses under pressure.
9. **Confidence-Boosting Programmes:** Initiate activities that improve self-esteem through team bonding, visualization exercises, and positive reinforcement.

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